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**AI in the Eye of the Beholder:
How Group Membership and AI Controllability Shapes User Acceptance**

Anna Monik¹ and Michał Parzuchowski²

¹ Institute of Psychology, Polish Academy of Sciences

² Center for Research on Cognition and Behavior, Department of Psychology, SWPS
University

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^{1*} Correspondence concerning this article should be addressed to Anna Monik, anna.monik@sd.psych.pan.pl

Abstract

Across two exploratory studies ($N = 747$), we examined how group identification and perceived AI's controllability shape the acceptance of AI. Our findings suggest that identification with opinion-based groups (AI fans vs. opponents) may determine differences in attitudes toward AI. Additionally, AI with intentions (high controllability) was more readily accepted than AI with emotions (low controllability). Yet, participants who strongly identified with AI supporters showed higher acceptance, particularly when interacting with AI with intentions. In contrast, low-identifying participants' attitudes remained stable across AI capabilities. These results indicate that group affiliations and perceptions of AI traits could form attitudes toward AI. Further research should investigate the influence of social identity and AI's ability to understand human mental states on user engagement.

Keywords: Artificial Intelligence, acceptance of AI, social identity, AI controllability, opinion-based groups

Upon its development, Artificial Intelligence (AI) and more specifically AI chatbots, generated substantial public interest and concern (Jiang et al., 2024)². Key considerations included the fear that AI might replace human workers (Vaast & Pinsonneault, 2021), or mimic a wide array of human traits (see Kaplan & Haenlein, 2019). A vast body of research revealed that public acceptance of AI was determined by factors like users' technological familiarity or cultural views on automation (Kelly et al., 2023). Worries were particularly high when AI was used for critical tasks, such as making unsupervised medical diagnoses (Yokoi et al., 2020), but were significantly lower when AI was assigned routine jobs, such as reviewing language or correcting prescriptions (Ali et al., 2023). Naturally, the approach towards AI may differ between enthusiasts and skeptics of AI development, particularly when they act in alignment with the collective self (Turner & Tajfel, 1986). Indeed, preferential attitudes, behaviours, or intentions often stem from group affiliation, especially when it is based on shared beliefs (Monik & Parzuchowski, 2024).

User acceptance of AI technologies has been studied from various theoretical perspectives. The Technology Acceptance Model (Davis, 1985) focuses on perceived usefulness and ease of use as key predictors of technology adoption. Similarly, the Unified Theory of Acceptance and Use of Technology (Venkatesh et al., 2003) examines individual factors like performance expectancy, social influence, effort expectancy, and facilitating conditions. The AI Device Use Acceptance model (Gursoy et al., 2019) includes three acceptance stages and six components: social influence, hedonic motivation, anthropomorphism, performance expectancy, effort expectancy, and emotion. Studies have consistently validated these models, showing that perceived usefulness, performance expectancy and effort expectancy were key predictors of AI adoption (Liu & Tao, 2022;

²AI is defined as an “unnatural object or entity that possesses the ability and capacity to meet or exceed the requirements of the task it is assigned when considering cultural and demographic circumstances” (Kelly et al., 2023, p. 2).

Strzelecki, 2023). These factors have been linked to AI use in public transport (Kuberkar & Singhal, 2020) or education (Kashive et al., 2020). Additionally, trust has substantially shaped user acceptance of AI (Schepman & Rodway, 2022). Zarifis and colleagues (2020) found that people exhibited higher trust and fewer privacy concerns when purchasing health insurance without visible AI. Similarly, trust in autonomous vehicles could be increased by ensuring data security and user control (Meyer-Waarden & Cloarec, 2022). Furthermore, peer approval amplified positive perceptions of AI (Chi et al., 2022). Nevertheless, none of these models sufficiently addressed group-related antecedents.

The purpose of this study is to explore whether psychosocial factors influence the acceptance of AI, namely if people identifying with the group of AI supporters are indeed more willing to approve and incorporate AI-fuelled solutions in everyday lives. Moreover, we aim to address the limited knowledge of how AI's perceived controllability - specifically its ability to experience emotions or form intentions - affects people's attitudes. We expected that individuals would be more inclined to accept AI agents capable of intention.

Group Dynamic on AI Acceptance

Social Identity Theory (Turner & Tajfel, 1986) states that individuals derive part of their self-concept from group affiliations, fostering preferences and favourable attitudes toward in-group members. Simply perceiving an out-group heightened the sense of threat to in-group distinctiveness and intensified in-group identification (Roccas & Schwartz, 1993). Social categorization has also been observed with artificial entities (Eyssel & Kuchenbrandt, 2012). For instance, studies have shown that artificial faces representing in-group members were perceived as more alive, more likely to possess a mind, experience pain, and devise plans than when these attributes were assigned to out-group faces (Krumhuber et al., 2015). Given these dynamics, we will examine two types of group identity as our predictors:

identification with an opinion-based community (seeing oneself as an AI supporter or opponent) and identification with all humanity (seeing oneself as a member of the entire human race; IWAH).

In the past decade, much research has focused on studies with human-robot dyads, showing that people react to robots in social interactions in similar (although not the same) ways to how they respond to humans (Mumm & Mutlu, 2011). Indeed, people used overlearned social behaviours, such as politeness or reciprocity, in their communication with computers. People expected human-like robots to follow human social norms (Syrdal et al., 2008), and applied stereotypes of human groups to robots (Bernotat et al., 2019). As AI entities become more social and more human-like, people may also feel greater empathy for them and treat AI applications more like (human) in-group members (see Vanman & Kappas, 2019). In this context, a particularly important question appears to be whether AI appearance activates one's intergroup perspective and how it shapes attitudes or behaviours towards AI-related issues.

People gathered around a shared worldview, regarded as an integral part of the collective aspect of the self, can constitute a separate group category that has a real impact on social reality through their actions (McGarty et al., 2009). Social identity within opinion-based communities has determined support for causes like global poverty, migration, and climate change (e.g., Hoskin et al., 2019; Thomas et al., 2020), but has also led to mobilization against vaccination and abortion laws (Maciuszek et al., 2021; Besta et al., 2019). In light of this evidence, identification with the AI-supporter community may shape social behaviour, influencing whom people associate with or support. Group affiliation may not only govern human-human interactions (Monik & Parzuchowski, 2024) but also affect AI-human relationships. Viewing AI through the lens of in-group favouritism or out-group

solidarity may influence the process of the adaptation of AI within society. Positive intergroup experiences can establish social norms geared toward cooperation with members of a supportive group. Conversely, when AI interacts with a group opposing its development, it may automatically perceive and categorize community members of as threatening, thereby amplifying antagonistic behaviours. Thus, it appears that opinion-based intergroup dynamics could have a profound impact on the patterns through which relationships with AI are shaped.

The second type of group identification (IWAH) has been significantly positively related to concern for global poverty and injustice, commitment to human rights, and support for international charities, while at the same time being negatively associated with ethnocentrism, right-wing authoritarianism, and social dominance (Hamer et al., 2019; McFarland et al., 2012). It can serve as a category, activating people's sense of common ground in the face of different social changes and challenges. Research to date has primarily focused on the impact of various aspects of robotization on the dynamics of human-human relationships, such as the reduction of intergroup prejudices mediated by panhumanism. Evidence has been optimistic, showing that the presence of robots (the out-group) can increase solidarity between human groups (Jackson et al., 2020). In a recent study, Wang and Peng (2023) demonstrated that AI experience positively predicted human identity, meaning that individuals with greater AI expertise might be more prone to view AI as an external group distinct from mankind, which therefore could enhance their subjective feeling of belongingness with all humans in the world. However, it has not been tested whether heightened identification with all humanity influences attitudes toward robots as a group.

Influence of Perceived Controllability on AI Acceptance

Judgments of control play a significant role in shaping our perceptions and responses to a broad range of social phenomena. Controllability refers to the influence one has over

their surroundings (Na et al., 2023). People tend to assimilate controllability information when evaluating the mental states of others (Lebowitz & Ahn, 2014). However, the degree of control varies by mental state. In six studies (2019) Cusimano and Goodwin demonstrated that lay people attribute to others a high degree of control over their mental states, with emotions systematically perceived to be lower in control than other kinds of mental states (e.g. beliefs, desires, evaluation), especially manifestations of intentions. Therefore, interacting with an agent showing emotions is a prototypical example of an uncontrollable experience, while communicating with the agent revealing intentions may serve as a prototypical example of a controllable experience.

The interplay of control and trust is crucial for the development and implementation of autonomous AI-driven systems (Castelfranchi & Falcone, 2000). In a broader sense, control can complement or even substitute trust, particularly when it helps reduce the probability of deviations, mistakes, or violations. Consequently, objects that can predictably interact with their environment and demonstrate control over their actions inspire more favourable attitudes among users (see Díaz-Rodríguez et al., 2023). The perception of controllability in AI may stem from the extent to which they are recognized as possessing human-like qualities. This connection is grounded in the fact that familiarity with being human serves as the most intuitive reference point for interpreting behavior (Broadbent, 2017). As a result, anthropomorphism—the attribution of human characteristics to non-human entities—shapes the way we infer mental states in AI systems. For example, the “o1-preview” chatGPT model displays a thinking-verifying-analysing status when generating its responses to users’ prompts, simulating deliberate human-like reasoning. Similarly, its predecessor, GPT-4o, was reportedly capable of identifying and interpreting users' emotions through voice. Those features may enhance the detection of the anthropomorphic capabilities of AI entities.

Yin and colleagues (2021) demonstrated that robots endowed with high mental capabilities generated more pronounced aversion compared to those with lower mental abilities. The aversion was evident regardless of the robot's physical appearance; participants felt significantly more unsettled when informed that a robot possessed certain cognitive faculties, whether it exhibited a human-like or mechanical form (Gray & Wegner, 2012). Similarly, efforts to imbue AI chatbots with emotional qualities, such as recognizing human emotions (Ong et al., 2019) or displaying facial expressions (Mishra et al., 2023), have been shown to provoke unease rather than enthusiasm among users. Appel and colleagues (2020) further explored this phenomenon by distinguishing between two dimensions of mental states in robots: experience (the capacity to feel) and agency (the capacity to plan and act). The findings revealed that robots endowed with the capacity to feel generated stronger feelings of eeriness than those capable of planning and self-regulation (agency). Complementing these findings, research on job displacement has highlighted heightened discomfort when individuals contemplate losing roles with emotional components to machines, as opposed to tasks requiring primarily cognitive skills (Waytz & Norton, 2014). Taken together, these findings indicate that individuals' perceptions of AI mental states significantly shape their reactions to these systems. Higher levels of emotional components may lead to decreased user acceptance.

Research Goals

This research aimed to explore the limit to how much people are willing to accept AI. We tested whether people's willingness to cooperate with AI could be rooted in the strength of identification with a meaningful social group based on shared opinion and broader with all humanity. Second, we hypothesized that people might exhibit a more disapproving stance towards AI with less predictable mental states (more fluent in operating beyond algorithmic

constraints). Lastly, we expected that group affiliation would influence attitudes toward AI depending on the mental states an AI application could simulate.

Thus far, no research has investigated the combined interplay of perceived controllability of AI and group identity on shaping users' attitudes toward AI. We predicted that users with stronger social identity with opinion-based group of AI supporters will be more likely to accept AI entity with highly controlled mental states (intention) than those with low controllability (emotion). The difference may be driven by the alignment of controllable AI with group norms prioritizing predictability and cooperation, while emotional AI may provoke unease due to its unpredictable nature. As mentioned, social identity fosters a sense of shared goals and cooperation within the in-group (Hoskin et al., 2019; McGarty et al., 2009). When AI systems exhibit intentionality, it signals predictability and agency, which aligns with group norms around trust and control (Castelfranchi & Falcone, 2000; Díaz-Rodríguez et al., 2023). That would be particularly appealing to groups advocating for AI adoption, as controllable AI can be framed as a reliable collaborator. Emotions are inherently less controllable, leading to interactions that feel unpredictable and unsettling (Cusimano & Goodwin, 2019; Ong et al., 2019). For participants in opinion-based groups, this unpredictability may contradict group norms emphasizing trust and control. Moreover, we expected that people with high level of IWAH would present less favorable approach towards AI, especially when it simulate emotions. AI displaying emotional expressions may be recognized as engaging in "human-like" social behaviors and evoke a sense of out-group threat (Jackson et al., 2020).

We conducted two studies to address these gaps in the literature. Study 1 examined if AI users' acceptance towards a humanlike AI chatbot (the App) could be predicted by two

social identities. In Study 2 we explored how both group identification and perceived AI controllability (AI mental states) interacted when explaining user acceptance.

Study 1

In Study 1, we explored the relationship between different types of group identification and attitudes towards AI. Specifically, we examined the level of acceptance of AI among high and low identifiers with the AI supporter community (social identity in an opinion-based group) and among high and low identifiers with all people in the world (human identity). We assumed that the acceptance of AI would be significantly higher among like-minded people with higher social identification, and acceptance of AI would be significantly lower among people identifying more strongly with all humankind. The full dataset is available on the Open Science Framework

https://osf.io/b2kyc/?view_only=f94514a5c154440f80ad71be2b7b9c6d.

Method

The participants were 342 students from a Polish university in exchange for partial course credit (74% women; $M_{age} = 27.5$ years, $SD = 7.88$). We excluded participants based on predetermined criteria: failed attention checks and low scores on a 10-item vocabulary test measuring English fluency (as the study was conducted in English). Participants completed an online survey via the Qualtrics platform individually and anonymously.

First, we asked participants to imagine that an AI-driven application, similar to ChatGPT, had recently been developed and carefully consider a groundbreaking genre of the application that had been designed to possess the capacity to experience sensations, have desires, engage in speculation, engage in thought processes, interact, and exhibit intentions, much like oneself and other individuals. Then, we measured the level of Acceptance of AI

with four items that ranged from 1 (*definitely not*) to 5 (*definitely yes*): “Please consider if you would like to use such App,” “How afraid you would be to come into contact with the App“, “Please consider whether you would support a government decision to fund the App”, “Would you support protests (e.g., sign a petition, participate in a demonstration, back crowdfunding project, post on your social media) against the government's decision to fund the App?”. Each question evaluated and averaged about 10 different mental states that the application was supposed to simulate (personality, morality, memory, intention, imagination, emotion, desire, deliberation, beliefs, and evaluation). The final score was the mean of four questions, where two items regarding fear of AI and collective action against AI were recoded.

Next, social identity in the opinion-based group was measured with a five-item scale (Bliuc et al., 2007) which captures similarity, content, identification, future and respect as different identity dimensions (e.g., “I am like the other people who support healthy eating for a healthy planet” [$\alpha = .91$]). The questions were adjusted in reference to the relevant group (AI development supporters). Participants rated their level of identity with each item using scales that ranged from 1 (*definitely not*) to 5 (*definitely yes*). Responses to items were averaged to create an overall index of social identity. The Cronbach's α reliability coefficient of the scale was .84.

Finally, to measure IWAH, a nine-item version of the Identification with All Humanity Scale was used (McFarland et al., 2012). Questions included, for example: “How close do you feel to each of the following groups?” and “How often do you use the word ‘we’ to refer to the following groups of people?” including identification with and concern for particular groups (from the immediate family to people all over the world). The raw score for identification with all humanity was the mean of the items asking about identification with

“people all over the world.” Responses were made on a 5-point Likert scale ranging from 1 (*not at all*) to 5 (*very close or very often*). The Cronbach's α reliability coefficient for IWAH was .86. To control the possible impact of individual factors, we also assessed several psychological traits, which have been demonstrated as significant for attitudes towards AI in previous studies. Park and Woo (2022) as well as Stein and colleagues (2024) showed that personality components like agreeableness exhibit a significant correlation with fear or acceptance of AI. User judgement about his ability to complete a specific task by using AI (Wang et al., 2021), and the tendency to actively engage in intensive technology interaction (Franke et al., 2019) have also been presented as a facilitator of favourable attitudes towards new technology. Taking into consideration those findings we evaluated: personality traits (10-Item Personality Inventory; Gosling et al., 2003), general self-efficacy (GSE, General Self-Efficacy Scale; Schwarzer & Jerusalem, 1995), self-esteem (RSE, 10-item Rosenberg Self-Esteem Scale; Rosenberg, 1979) and affinity for technology interaction (ATI, 9-item scale; Franke et al., 2019).

Results

To determine if the level of acceptance of AI was indeed higher for high identifiers with supporters of AI, we conducted a regression analysis. Results illustrated in Table 1 indicated that the higher the level of social identity with AI supporters the higher the level of Acceptance of AI ($b = .38, p < .001$). To test the second hypothesis concerning IWAH, we also performed a regression analysis. Contrary to our predictions, no significant effect has been found ($b = -.03, p = .57$), which stated that identification with all humanity is not associated with the level of Acceptance of AI.

Additionally, a multiple regression analysis was conducted to examine the predictors of acceptance of AI, including demographic information, psychological and psychosocial

variables³. As showed in Table 2, the model incorporating group factors significantly improved the fit compared to the model based on individual components ($R^2 = .31$, $\Delta R^2 = .17$, $F(2,327) = 38.9$, $p < .001$). Social identity with the opinion-based group was a strong predictor, positively associated with acceptance of AI ($b = .34$, $p < .001$), while IWAH was associated negatively ($b = -.10$, $p = .016$). Moreover, emotional stability ($b = -.06$, $p = .038$) and GSE ($b = .02$, $p = .019$) were also positive predictors of a favourable approach towards AI. These results suggest that among diverse individual traits and intergroup contributors, social identity (identifying as an AI supporter) showed the strongest positive relation with users' approving attitudes towards AI.

Study 2

The aim of this study was to further explore the relationship between different types of group identification and attitudes towards AI (social identity in opinion-based groups and identification with all humanity). We retained the same hypotheses as those formulated in Study 1. The novelty of the research consisted of the examination of whether AI systems described as having high controllability of mental states (intentions) would elicit higher levels of acceptance of AI compared to AI described as having low controllability (emotions). Furthermore, we predicted that participants with greater social identity in opinion-based groups would declare more accepting attitudes towards AI, particularly when interacting with AI systems described as having high controllability of mental state. Conversely, we expected that participants with greater identification with all humanity would declare less accepting attitudes towards AI, particularly when interacting with AI systems described as having low controllability of mental states. The study was pre-registered at OSF

³ In both studies in hierarchical regression models the variables social identity in opinion based group and group identification with all humanity were tested for the groups of low and high identifiers, based on median split

https://osf.io/yrmx9/?view_only=514cf3ae42274f5ab91403833b26c78b The full dataset is available on OSF https://osf.io/b2kyc/?view_only=f94514a5c154440f80ad71be2b7b9c6d.

Method

A sample of 405 English-speaking participants was recruited through the Prolific research platform (56% women; $M_{age} = 30.6$ years; $SD = 9.73$). We offered a small compensation for completing a brief online questionnaire (\$1 US). We excluded participants based on predetermined criteria: failed control questions concerning project description and failed attention checks.

First, we asked participants to categorize themselves as AI development supporters or opponents. Then, we displayed a description of an AI-driven application, similar to ChatGPT that was designed to possess different mental states. In Study 2 we manipulated how controllable was the ability of the AI App: half of the respondents learned that the App was capable of having a human-like Intentions and the other half were learning that the App was able to have human-like Emotions. The mental state operationalization was incorporated from Cusimao and Goodwin's research (2019). The initial list of items with verbs describing having emotions (15 items) and intentions (11 items) has been evaluated by five competent judges in terms of clarity (is it understandable what the app can do) and realism (is it easy to imagine that the app could do that particular thing) a scale of 1-5. As a result, the final three items with the highest scores (3.6 and above) for each mental state have been selected. In the Emotion condition participants read that the App could (1) *feel happy when receiving a perfect score on the previous task*, (2) *feel sad when learning it needs to improve on the next try*, and (3) *feel anxious to finish the work in a quicker way than before*. In the Intention condition participants learned that the App could (1) *set a goal to receive a perfect score on the upcoming task*, (2) *on its own plan to improve on the next try*, and (3) *resolve to finish the*

work in a quicker way than before. Next, a short description of the group task was provided, in which all participants were to collaborate with other people and the application to promote the use of AI in everyday life⁴. Following this, we measured the level of AI Acceptance, and social identity in the opinion-based group: as a supporter ($\alpha = .85$) or opponent ($\alpha = .79$), and IWAH ($\alpha = .87$) using the same scales as in Study 1. We also assessed ATI since it was the strongest correlate in Study 1.

Results

We hypothesized that AI supporters would be more accepting of AI. We also expected that people with higher levels of IWAH would be less accepting of AI. Moreover, we anticipated that the stronger the controllability of the simulated mental state the more positive the perception of AI. In addition, we predicted that the greater the group identification with AI supporters, the more favourable the attitude toward AI, but only for the App with intentions. Eventually, we hypothesized that the greater the group identification with humankind, the less favourable the attitude toward AI, but only for the App with emotions.

To test these predictions, we conducted a regression analysis presented in Table 1, that revealed that the higher the level of social identity with AI supporters the higher the level of Acceptance of AI ($b = .54, p < .001$). The same effect was found in the AI opponents group ($b = -.77, p < .001$). A positive association was also shown between IWAH and acceptance of AI ($b = .17, p < .001$). Afterwards, we ran a regression analysis that showed a

⁴ Instruction of the group task in Study 2: “Now, imagine that one of your friends invites you to join a group project focused on advancing artificial intelligence (AI). In this group, you would work alongside other people but also cooperate with the App and similar AI applications to create content that promotes the benefits of integrating AI technology into everyday life. The content generated by this collective effort would serve to educate individuals and raise public awareness of the many benefits of using AI. Additionally, it would foster a community that brings together diverse entities, including the App and other AI applications, to support the continued progress of AI.”

significant difference in the level of AI acceptance depending on the simulated mental state. As predicted, the experimental group with the Intention condition had a higher level of acceptance of AI compared to the Emotion condition ($b = .22, p < .01$).

Finally, we validated the interaction between social identity and mental states. As presented in Table 3, a regression analysis showed that in the group of high identifiers with AI supporters, attitudes towards AI were more accepting, particularly when interacting with the App described as having high controllability of mental states ($b = .25, p < .034$). Simultaneously, the main effect of the social identity in opinion-based group has been demonstrated. Those who identified stronger with AI supporters declared more accepting attitudes towards AI ($b = .44, p < .001$). However, no main effect of mental states has been observed. Participants who imagined the App as having intentions did not exhibit a higher level of acceptance of AI compared to when it was capable of simulating emotions ($b = .01, p < .885$). Additionally, a regression analysis showed no significant interaction effect between AI mental state and identification with all humanity ($b = .23, p < .118$). Both main effects for identification ($b = .08, p < .462$) and mental state ($b = .10, p < .385$) have not been valid.

A multiple regression analysis was conducted to examine individual and group predictors of acceptance of AI, including the interaction between identification with AI supporters and the controllability of AI mental state (emotion vs. intention). As illustrated in Table 4, Model 2 incorporating group factors significantly improved the fit compared to model 1 based on individual components ($R^2 = .24, \Delta R^2 = .17, F(3,366) = 8.15, p < .001$). The more advanced model 3, confirming the significant interaction effect (social identity x AI controllability), refined data fit compared to model 2 ($R^2 = .25, \Delta R^2 = .01, F(1,362) = 4.22, p < .041$).

General Discussion

The main purpose of the two reported studies was to examine psychological factors underlying attitudes toward AI acceptance. In particular, we examined how psychosocial components (group identification) may determine differences in positive attitudes toward advanced, interactive technology. Secondly, we investigated the role of perceived AI controllability (different mental states possessed by the App) in the acceptance of AI. Furthermore, we aimed to evaluate the possible interaction between AI controllability (mental states) and social attributes (group identification) on human reactions to AI. Our findings demonstrated that social identity is a substantial differentiating factor in discerning attitudes towards AI. Results were in line with the assumptions of Social Identity Theory, which posits that an individual's sense of self is derived from their group membership, leading to the adaptation of the group's norms, values, and behaviours. The degree to which individuals identify with AI opinion-based groups correlated strongly with people's attitudes toward AI. Studies confirmed that acceptance of AI was significantly stronger in a group of like-minded people with higher social identification. Contradicting our prediction, people who strongly considered themselves to be members of the global community (identification with all humanity) manifested substantially increased (not diminished) levels of AI endorsement. However, that result occurred only in Study 2. It is noteworthy that social identity in an opinion-based group remained the strongest predictor of acceptance of AI, showing higher contribution than individual factors like personality, age, gender, self-esteem or digital fluency.

The research showed that positive attitudes towards AI varied based on the perceived controllability of simulated mental state, which has not been extensively studied before. Consistent with the hypothesis, AI described as being able to express intentions (high

controllability) elicited higher levels of acceptance of AI than AI described as having emotions (low controllability). Moreover, results revealed that the effect of group affiliation on attitudes toward AI could differ depending on the types of mental states that a given application is capable of simulating. Notably, in a group of high identifiers with AI supporters, attitudes toward AI were more accepting, particularly when interacting with the App described as having high controllability of mental state (Intention), whereas, among the low identifiers group, positive attitudes were at a comparable level regardless of the mental state. The effect was not observed for group affiliation based on IWAH.

People are and will increasingly interact with AI, making it essential to explore how this affects human behaviour at both individual and group levels. Our findings support the Computers are Social Actors (CASA) paradigm (Reeves & Nass, 1996), which suggests that people engage socially with media, applying the same social heuristics they use in human interactions because computers evoke similar social attributes. Specifically, we establish that similar psychosocial mechanisms operate in interactions with AI as in human-to-human interactions. Our conclusions enhance the understanding of which social categories may be activated and in what contexts these interaction patterns can be replicated. Exposure to AI triggers group identification processes, shaping attitudes and behaviours related to AI—such as technology usage, fear of AI, support for AI funding, or collective action against its development. These observations confirm that studies focusing solely on individual perceptions and behaviours toward AI, without considering group membership, overlook a critical factor: group dynamics (see Smith et al., 2021).

In this exploratory study, we aimed to examine social identity from two perspectives: AI as an in-group member (within opinion-based groups) and AI as an out-group member (IWAH). The findings suggest that social identity is crucial for analysing modern challenges,

such as AI development (Monik & Parzuchowski, 2024). It not only polarizes society but also fosters strong group affiliations that provide a foundation for specific behaviours. The sense of belonging to a shared opinion-based group appears to be a key inclusive category, positioning AI entities like ChatGPT, as potential in-group members. This implies that such applications may be perceived not only as interaction partners but also as full-fledged members of the in-group. Accordingly, people may incorporate a wide range of in-group bias consequences when interacting with AI, leading to more inclusive behaviours and deeper integration of technology into social structure (see Deligianis et al., 2017).

Surprisingly, IWAH results showed an inverse relationship to our expectations. Specifically, a stronger sense of panhumanism was linked to more favourable attitudes toward technological advancement. Wang and Peng (2023) suggested that it may indicate that our sample had a high level of AI competence, though this seems unlikely given the group's diversity. Paradoxically, increased solidarity with humanity might have reduced perceived threats from AI. However, Study 1, conducted on students, found no significant differences in attitudes towards AI. Contrary to the findings of Wang and Peng (2023), frequent AI interactions and their normalization may prevent AI from being seen as an out-group or a threat to human distinctiveness (Cha et al., 2020). Further research is encouraged to explore this aspect in greater depth.

Previous studies (e.g., Mara et al., 2022; Mathur et al., 2020) have focused on the anthropomorphizing of humanoid robots, but attention should also be given to large language models (LLMs) and how their ability to simulate human cognitive and emotional states is perceived. Our study shows that AI becomes unsettling when perceived as having experiences (the ability to feel) rather than just agency (the ability to act) (e.g., Appel et al., 2020; Gray & Wegner, 2012). This aligns with the findings of Koban and Banks (2024), who

suggested that an AI's emotional capacity determines whether it is seen as a mindful agent. Emotional engagement by social robots can lead to expectancy violations and dehumanization (Haslam et al., 2008), resulting in more negative attitudes than AI which only displays cognitive abilities. Our insights confirm this pattern with non-humanoid AI, which is the most commonly encountered form of AI.

AI-human similarity affects attitudes more for high-identifiers when AI is perceived as part of the ingroup, though AI entities may be viewed as less prototypical ingroup members (Van Knippenberg, 2011). According to social identity theory (Turner & Tajfel, 1986), prototypical members have greater influence within their group (Hogg, 2001). Our results suggest that group effects may extend to human-robot interactions, though to a lesser extent than human-human relations (e.g., Fraune, 2020). According to another hypothesis, the potential source of such logic may be related to intragroup dynamics, where some division between AI and human members persists. Opinion-based groups focus on shared goals, often minimizing barriers to collaboration, but AI's uncontrollable and omnipotent nature could create perceived barriers, especially for individuals with stronger group identities invested in maintaining cohesion. Future research should explore this further. Conversely, when AI is viewed as an outgroup, AI-human similarity has less impact on attitudes among high-identifiers. Since AI interaction does not deepen intergroup divisions, people may not feel threatened by AI. Non-humanoid, non-material AI may not be seen as a real threat, making control concerns secondary. This aligns with the findings of Wang and Peng (2023) who emphasized the role of perceived anthropomorphism and perceived proximity as essential prerequisites for AI to be considered an outgroup of humans.

Limitations and future directions

The current paper has several limitations. First, both studies relied on self-reported judgments; replicating the research using interactions with an actual AI application would be beneficial. Second, Study 2 examined only two mental states out of the many that AI can simulate (e.g., imagination, morality, personality); testing a wider range could reveal more about group mechanisms and subtle differences. Third, strengthening group identity activation in the experiment could validate the hypotheses across different contexts, particularly by framing AI as either an ingroup or outgroup member. Finally, we did not directly measure perceived threat of AI, which would have further explored our hypotheses.

Research on human-AI intergroup relations is still in its early stages. The exploratory studies we have presented here show that general patterns of human-human interaction may, to some extent, apply to human-AI contacts. However, individual characteristics of AI—like its similarity to humans or perceived controllability—seem to play a moderating role in the processes. As social psychologists, we are called upon to provide essential expertise and conduct research aimed at reducing prejudices toward AI entities and facilitating their successful integration into society. The field specializing in group identity seems particularly noteworthy in this context.

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Table 1

Regression indices for group identification factors predicting Acceptance of AI

Predictor	Study 1				Study 2			
	<i>b</i>	<i>b</i> 95% CI [LL, UL]	<i>beta</i>	<i>beta</i> 95% CI [LL, UL]	<i>b</i>	<i>b</i> 95% CI [LL, UL]	<i>beta</i>	<i>beta</i> 95% CI [LL, UL]
Identification with opinion-based group of AI supporters	.38**	[.31, .45]	.50**	[.41, .60]	.54**	[-.46, -.63]	.56**	[.47, .64]
Identification with all the humanity	-.03	[-.12, .07]	-.03	[-.14, .08]	.17**	[.08, .27]	.18**	[.08, .28]

Note. *b* represents unstandardized regression weights. *beta* indicates the standardized regression weights. *LL* and *UL* indicate the lower and upper limits of a confidence interval, respectively.

* $p < .05$. ** $p < .01$.

Table 2

Regression indices for individual factors (model 1) and social factors (model 2) predicting Acceptance of AI

Predictor	<i>b</i>	<i>b</i> 95% CI [LL, UL]	<i>beta</i>	<i>b</i> 95% CI [LL, UL]	Fit	Difference
(Intercept)	2.01**	[1.45, 2.58]				
Gender	.22**	[.06, .39]	.36**	[.10, .62]		
Age	-.01	[-.02, .00]	-.09	[-.20, .02]		
Extraversion	-.01	[-.07, .04]	-.03	[-.14, .09]		
Agreeableness	.04	[-.03, .11]	.06	[-.05, .18]		
Conscientiousness	.03	[-.04, .09]	.05	[-.07, .17]		
Emotional stability	-.06	[-.12, .00]	-.12	[-.25, .01]		
Openness to experience	.03	[-.04, .11]	.05	[-.07, .17]		
ATI	.16**	[.08, .24]	.23**	[.12, .34]		
GSE	.02*	[.01, .04]	.18*	[.05, .31]		
RSE	-.00	[-.02, .01]	-.02	[-.02, .12]		
					<i>Model 1: R</i> ² =	
					.145**	
(Intercept)	1.84**	[1.30, 2.39]				
Gender	.19*	[.05, .31]	.31*	[.07, .55]		
Age	.00	[-.01, .01]	-.04	[-.13, .06]		
Extraversion	-.01	[-.06, .03]	-.03	[-.13, .07]		
Agreeableness	.03	[-.02, .10]	.05	[-.05, .16]		
Conscientiousness	.01	[-.04, .07]	.02	[-.08, .13]		
Emotional stability	-.06*	[-.11, -.01]	-.12*	[-.24, .07]		
Openness to experience	.03	[-.04, .10]	.05	[-.06, .15]		
ATI	.07	[.01, .14]	.10	[.00, .21]		
GSE	.02*	[.00, .03]	.14*	[.02, .26]		
RSE	-.01	[-.02, .01]	-.06	[-.18, .07]		
Identification with humanity	-.10*	[-.19, -.02]	-.12*	[-.22, -.02]		
Identification with opinion-based	.34**	[.26, .41]	.44**	[.34, .55]		

group

$$\begin{array}{l} \text{Model 2: } R^2 = \\ .314^{**} \end{array} \quad \begin{array}{l} \Delta R^2 = \\ .169^{**} \end{array}$$

Note. *b* represents unstandardized regression weights. *beta* indicates the standardized regression weights. *LL* and *UL* indicate the lower and upper limits of a confidence interval, respectively.

* $p < .05$. ** $p < .01$.

Table 3

Regression indices for interaction between group identification and mental states predicting Acceptance of AI in Study 2

	<i>b</i>	<i>b</i> 95% CI [LL, UL]	<i>beta</i>	<i>beta</i> 95% CI [LL, UL]
Identification with opinion-based group of AI supporters	.44**	[.27, .61]	.35*	[.21, .48]
AI mental state (intention)	.01	[-.14, .16]	.19	[.01, .37]
Identification with opinion-based group of AI supporters x AI mental state	.25*	[.02, .48]	.20	[.01, .38]
Identification with humanity	.08	[-.13, .28]	.05	[-.09, .19]
AI mental state (intention)	.10	[-.12, .30]	.29	[.09, .48]
Identification with humanity x AI mental state	.23	[-.06, .52]	.15	[-.04, .35]

Note. *b* represents unstandardized regression weights. *beta* indicates the standardized regression weights. *LL* and *UL* indicate the lower and upper limits of a confidence interval, respectively.

* $p < .05$. ** $p < .01$.

Table 4

Regression indices for individual factors (model 1), social factors (model 2) and the interaction between experimental manipulation and opinion-based social identity (model 3) predicting Acceptance of AI

Predictor	<i>b</i>	<i>b</i> 95% CI [LL, UL]	<i>beta</i>	<i>b</i> 95% CI [LL, UL]	Fit	Difference
(Intercept)	3.04**	[2.61, 3.46]				
Gender	.12	[-.01, .24]	.18	[-.02, .38]		
Age	.00	[-.01, .01]	.02	[-.08, .12]		
Affinity for technology	.20**	[.12, .28]	.24**	[.14, .34]	$R^2 = .006$	
(Intercept)	3.20**	[2.79, 3.60]				
Gender	.04	[-.08, .16]	.07	[-.12, .26]		
Age	.00	[-.00, .01]	.05	[-.05, .14]		
Affinity for technology	.09*	[.01, .17]	.11*	[.01, .20]		
Identifiers with humanity	.02	[-.10, .14]	.01	[-.08, .11]		
Identifiers with AI supporters group	.53**	[.40, .65]	.41**	[.32, .51]		
AI mental state (intention)	.13*	[.02, .25]	.21*	[.02, .39]	$R^2 = .236**$	$\Delta R^2 = .173**$
(Intercept)	3.25**	[2.85, 3.66]				
Gender	.04	[-.08, .16]	.06	[-.13, .25]		
Age	.00	[-.00, .01]	.05	[-.04, .14]		
Affinity for technology	.08*	[.01, .16]	.10*	[.01, .20]		
Identifiers with humanity	.01	[-.12, .13]	.00	[-.09, .10]		
Identifiers with AI supporters group	.40**	[.22, .57]	.31**	[.18, .45]		
AI mental state (intention)	.03	[-.12, .18]	.21	[.03, .40]		
Identifiers with AI supporters group * AI	.24*	[.01, .48]	.19*	[.01, .37]		

mental state (intention)

$$R^2 = .245^{**} \quad \Delta R^2 = .009^*$$

Note. *b* represents unstandardized regression weights. *beta* indicates the standardized regression weights. *LL* and *UL* indicate the lower and upper limits of a confidence interval, respectively.

* $p < .05$. ** $p < .01$.